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Introduction

According to GeeksforGeeks (2024), “Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that enables algorithms to uncover hidden patterns within datasets, allowing them to make predictions on new, similar data without explicit programming for each task. Traditional machine learning combines data with statistical tools to predict outputs, yielding actionable insights. This technology finds applications in diverse fields such as image and speech recognition, natural language processing, recommendation systems, fraud detection, portfolio optimization, and automating tasks. For instance, recommender systems use historical data to personalize suggestions.” Upnify Editorial Team (2024) also stated that “Machine learning offers several important advantages over other data analysis methods. These advantages include the ability to process large amounts of data in a short time and automate complex tasks. Here are three important advantages of machine learning: 1. Accurate prediction: Machine learning makes it possible to predict the future with increasing accuracy, thanks to machine learning algorithms that learn from experience. This is especially useful in marketing, where consumer trends can be predicted more accurately. It is also useful in healthcare, where treatment outcomes can be determined more accurately. 2. Cost reduction: Machine learning can reduce costs for businesses by automating complex tasks that would otherwise be time-consuming and resource-intensive. For example, machine learning can classify emails according to their importance. This can significantly reduce employees' time reading irrelevant emails.”

This report aims to build a machine learning model by using Linear Regression Mode to solve a real-world problem and prepare a report and presentation summarizing the findings. A dataset is from a web application of a company called ‘PTC WORKSHOPS’ located in Kampot province, Cambodia. The main functionalities of the current management system of this company are the management of vehicle repair services and vehicle spare part sales. The database of the company is exported to a CSV file to work with Python programming language for analysis purposes titled “**Linear Regression Model for Predicting Company Income Using Service Frequency**”. The criteria include problem formulation and data preparation, model selection and training, model interpretation and evaluation, and AI Ethics and Fairness.

Main Body

1. Problem Formulation and Data Cleaning and Preparation

There are 1 table out of 17 tables is chosen to use in the machine learning for prediction. It is ‘table_invoice’ that stores data of invoices when customers pay fee after they received the vehicle services.

Table	Action
<input type="checkbox"/> table_type	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_admin	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_attendance	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_car	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> table_invoice	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_invoice_detail	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_invoice_detail_temp	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_payment	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_product	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_role	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_salary	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_service_income	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_staff	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_staff_type	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_stock	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_summary	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
<input type="checkbox"/> table_utility	★ Browse Structure Search Insert Empty
17 tables	Sum

Figure 1. All tables in MySQL database of PTC WORKSHOPS company

In ‘table_invoice’ has 12 columns with difference data types from ‘PTC WORKSHOPS’ company as the showing in ‘figure 2’.

invoice_id	invoice_date	customer_name	customer_phone	plate_number	staff_id	sub_total	discount	grand_total	payment	paid	admin_id
12597	2024-07-01 17:17:33	Highlander	0	2AP 0690	19	5	0	5	5	1	0
12596	2024-07-01 17:16:29	Nissan	0	2B 1128	18	5	0	5	5	1	0
12595	2024-07-01 16:17:24	Prius 07	0	ázgáZáYáz·aYáz·ázfázéáz·aYáz	21	30	0	30	30	1	0
12594	2024-07-01 16:10:26	Morning 07	0	2C 0234	38	10	0	10	10	1	0
12593	2024-07-01 16:00:43	Sinco	0	2AQ 7119	18	5	0	5	5	1	0
12592	2024-07-01 15:42:43	Lexus RX 300	0	2B 3713	18	63.25	0	63.25	63.25	1	0
12591	2024-07-01 15:35:09	Highlander	0	2B 3393	18	41	0	41	41	1	0
12590	2024-07-01 15:21:16	Tacoma 06	0	2BJ 5542	23	38	0	38	38	1	0
12589	2024-07-01 14:56:40	Ford	0	2AB 7213	21	15	0	15	15	1	0
12588	2024-07-01 14:54:39	Lexus RX 330	0	2AQ 7895	19	15	0	15	15	1	0
12587	2024-07-01 14:53:40	Ford	0	ázgáZáYáz·aYáz·ázfázéáz·aYáz	15	5	0	5	5	1	0

Figure 2. Data in 'table_invoice' table

1.1. Problem Formulation

The aim of this analysis is to develop Linear Regression model that can predict the income of the company based on the service frequency that provided by the company's dataset. To understand the relationship between service's income and frequency, the company can make a frequency distribution table that has two main columns or variables are dependent variable (target) and independent variable (predictor). The company income is used to be a dependent variable that stores the service's income performed by the company over a specified period. Service frequency is used to be an independent variable to store number of services provided by the company within the same period. The assumptions of the prediction, there is a linear relationship between the service frequency provided and the company's income to build a reliable predictive model. The model assumes that other factors influencing income are either constant or have minimal impact compared to service frequency. The expected outcome of the analysis aims to produce a linear regression model that estimates the company's income based on the given service's frequency accurately and provides insights into the strength and nature of the relationship between service frequency and the company's income as indicated by metrics such as R-squared and Mean Squared Error (MSE). Moreover, the model can be used to forecast and plan purposes to improve the business's operations. The challenges of the Linear Regression Model are its accuracy may be affected by outliers, missing data, or non-linear relationships that are not captured by Linear regression. For external factors not included in the model, including market conditions or operational costs, can influence income and limit the predictive power of the model.


```

InvoiceRemoveUTF8.py > ...
1  import pandas as pd
2  import re
3  filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
4  dataframe = pd.read_csv(filePath, encoding='utf-8')
5  def isLatin(plateNumber):
6      if pd.isna(plateNumber):
7          return False
8      return bool(re.match(r'^[\u0020-\u007E]+$', plateNumber))
9  dataframeCleaned = dataframe[dataframe['plate_number'].apply(isLatin)]
10 dataframeCleaned.to_csv(filePath, index=False, encoding='utf-8')

```

Figure 4. Python code to remove 'Khmer Unicode' values in 'plate_number' column

After executing 'InvoiceRemoveUTF8.py' file, rows of 'Khmer Unicode' values in 'plate_number' column have been removed from the dataset. And the new data will be written back to the existing CSV after completing this task.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	invoice_id	invoice_date	customer_name	customer_phone	plate_number	staff_id	sub_total
2	1	#####	Lexus RX 300	93619478	2D 4457	29	71
3	2	#####	Camry 02		0 2A 6409	31	40
4	3	#####	Camry 02		0 2A 6409	31	40
5	4	#####	Camry 02		0 2C 7200	18	51
6	5	#####	Lexus RX 300		0 2AJ 2583	18	53
7	6	#####	Visto		0 2A 2415	18	80
8	8	#####	Prius 06		0 2AT 0624	21	58

Figure 5. Values in 'plate_number' column of 'Invoice.csv' after removing 'Khmer Unicode'

1.3. Data Normalization

Data normalization is a technique that used to transform the values of a dataset into a common scale. This is important because the dataset in statistics is sensitive to the scale of the input features and can produce better results when the data is normalized. In this case, percentile is one of the normalization techniques that is used to separate the data into 100 equal segments. The percentile data normalization is used to remove some outlier segments by using from the 5% lowest percentile until the highest 95%. The formula of percentile is $P = (n/N) \times 100$. Where 'P'

is percentile, 'n' is number of values below number of fall values, 'N' is total count of population. By using Python programming to solve this case is one of the best ways in analysis (GeeksforGeeks, 2024b). A file names 'InvoiceNormalize.py' is used to read 'Invoices.csv' and calculate the lowest percentile 5% and the highest 5% of the dataset. Before performing the highest of 'grand_total' value is 3212 and the lowest of 'grand_total' value is 0.

	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	plate_number	staff_id	sub_total	discount	grand_total	payment	paid	admin_id
2	2C 7799	19	3212	0	3212	3212	1	0
3	2BJ 0785	18	2326	0	2326	2326	1	0
4	2AW 0331	19	1938.5	0	1938.5	1938.5	1	0
5	2CA 9869	24	1925	0	1925	1925	1	0
6	2BY 6406	12	1883	0	1883	1883	1	0

Figure 6. Highest value (3212 USD) in 'grand_total' column before removing

	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
12052	2BM 8194	32	0	0	0	0	1	0
12053	2AM 6386	22	0	0	0	0	1	0
12054	2G 5448	21	0	0	0	0	1	0
12055	2AP 2799	15	0	0	0	0	1	0
12056	2AK 8359	58	0	0	0	0	1	0

Figure 7. Lowest value (0 USD) in 'grand_total' column before removing

```

InvoiceNormalize.py > ...
1  import pandas as pd
2  file_path = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
3  data = pd.read_csv(file_path)
4  column = 'grand_total'
5  Q1 = data[column].quantile(0.05)
6  Q3 = data[column].quantile(0.95)
7  filtered_data = data[(data[column] >= Q1) & (data[column] <= Q3)]
8  filtered_data.to_csv(file_path, index=False)

```

Figure 8. Python code to normalize dataset

The 'InvoiceNormalize.py' code removed the lowest 5% and highest 5% rows of 'grand_total' values from the dataset but keep the new data after this process is from 5% to 95% only. And the new data will be written back to the existing CSV file after completing this task. After the performing the highest of 'grand_total' value is 220 and the lowest of 'grand_total' value is 5.

	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	plate_number	staff_id	sub_total	discount	grand_total	payment	paid	admin_id
2	2A 5022	29	220	0	220	220	1	0
3	2BH 3161	11	220	0	220	220	1	0
4	2W 9295	29	220	0	220	220	1	0
5	2A 4487	19	220	0	220	220	1	0
6	2C 9711	28	220	0	220	220	1	0

Figure 9. Higher value (220 USD) in 'grand_total' column after removing

	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
11245	2N 7443	12	5	0	5	5	1	0
11246	2X 7130	23	5	0	5	5	1	0
11247	2AQ 7119	18	5	0	5	5	1	0
11248	2B 1128	18	5	0	5	5	1	0
11249	2AP 0690	19	5	0	5	5	1	0

Figure 10. Lowest value (5 USD) in 'grand_total' column after removing

1.4. Feature Engineering

A website (*Feature Engineering for Machine Learning - JavatPoint*, n.d.) wrote that “Feature engineering is the pre-processing step of machine learning, which extracts features from raw data. It helps to represent an underlying problem to predictive models in a better way, which as a result, improve the accuracy of the model for unseen data. The predictive model contains predictor variables and an outcome variable, and while the feature engineering process selects the most useful predictor variables for the model.”. One of another Feature Engineering is Frequency Distribution, it is a table that display frequency of group of values. The 'Invoices.csv' dataset will be used to construct the frequency distribution table of 'frequency' and 'amount' of 'plate_number' values. Because of the values of 'customer_name' column are not appropriate, 'plate_number' is used to count to be 'frequency' instead of 'customer_name'.

```

FrequencyTableInvoice.py > ...
1  import pandas as pd
2  filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
3  dataframe = pd.read_csv(filePath)
4  result = dataframe.groupby('plate_number').agg(
5      frequency=('plate_number', 'size'),
6      amount=('grand_total', 'sum')
7  ).reset_index()
8  result = result.sort_values(by='frequency', ascending=False)
9  result.to_csv(filePath, index=False)

```

Figure 11. Python code to create distribution frequency table

After completing the code execution, 'Invoice.csv' has been transformed to Frequency Distribution by storing data in 3 columns only are 'plate_number', 'frequency' and 'amount'. So, now 'Invoice.csv' is the Frequency Distribution form that will be used in Linear Regression Model of Machine Learning in next phase.

	A	B	C
1	plate_number	frequency	amount
2	2C 8080	51	2965.5
3	2AW 0022	32	1926.75
4	2S 0948	29	1243.5
5	2AL 3580	28	1046
6	2A 7089	27	1052.5
7	2B 4447	23	1480.5
8	2C 2788	21	1211

Figure 12. Distribution Frequency Table of 'Invoice.csv'

2. Model Selection and Training

2.1. Selection of Appropriate Algorithms

```

LinearRegressionPTCWorkshop.py > ...
1  import pandas as pd
2  from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV, cross_val_score
3  from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression, Ridge, Lasso
4  from sklearn.metrics import r2_score, mean_squared_error
5  import numpy as np
6  # Load the dataset
7  filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
8  data = pd.read_csv(filePath)
9  # Specify the feature (X) and target (y) variables
10 X = data[['frequency']] # Replace with the actual feature column name
11 y = data['amount']      # Replace with the actual target column name
12 # Split the data into training and testing sets
13 XTrain, XTest, yTrain, yTest = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
14 # Define the models to evaluate
15 models = {
16     'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),
17     'Ridge': Ridge(),
18     'Lasso': Lasso()
19 }
20 # Define the hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso
21 paramGrid = {
22     'Ridge': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]},
23     'Lasso': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]}
24 }
25 # Store the best models after hyperparameter tuning
26 bestModels = {}
27 for name, model in models.items():
28     if name in paramGrid:
29         # Perform hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV
30         gridSearch = GridSearchCV(model, paramGrid[name], cv=5, scoring='r2')
31         gridSearch.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
32         bestModels[name] = gridSearch.best_estimator_
33     else:
34         # Fit the model without hyperparameter tuning
35         model.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
36         bestModels[name] = model
37 # Evaluate the performance of the best models
38 for name, model in bestModels.items():
39     yPred = model.predict(XTest)
40     r2 = r2_score(yTest, yPred)
41     mse = mean_squared_error(yTest, yPred)
42     print(f"Model: {name}")
43     print(f"R-squared: {r2:.2f}")
44     print(f"Mean Squared Error: {mse:.2f}")
45     print("-" * 30)
46 # Cross-validation for the best model
47 bestModelName = max(bestModels, key=lambda name: r2_score(yTest, bestModels[name].predict(XTest)))
48 bestModel = bestModels[bestModelName]
49 crossValScores = cross_val_score(bestModel, X, y, cv=5, scoring='r2')
50 print(f"Best Model: {bestModelName}")
51 print(f"Cross-validated R-squared: {np.mean(crossValScores):.2f} ± {np.std(crossValScores):.2f}")

```

Figure 13. Python code of Linear Regression Model

There are many types of regression models, including Simple Regression, Multiple Regression, Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression, and Logistic Regression. Simple Regression estimates the relationship between a dependent variable (amount column) and one independent variable (frequency column). The Multiple Linear Regression shows that the direct or linear correlation between variables is possible. For this analysis, Linear Regression is chosen, as it aligns with the focused title of the report.

Output:

```
Model: LinearRegression
R-squared: 0.72
Mean Squared Error: 8579.35
-----
Model: Ridge
R-squared: 0.72
Mean Squared Error: 8588.03
-----
Model: Lasso
R-squared: 0.72
Mean Squared Error: 8585.22
-----
Best Model: LinearRegression
Cross-validated R-squared: 0.18 ± 0.23
```

Figure 14. The result of Linear Regression Model after analysis from Distribution Frequency Table of PTC WORKSHOPS company dataset

The output result after executing the file names ‘**LinearRegression.py**’ are displayed by divided to LinearRegression, Ridge, and Lasso, Best Model: LinearRegression and Cross-validated R-squared. The output of the R-squared value in Model: LinearRegression is 0.72 means that the model is 72% of the variance in the ‘amount’ column (dependent variable), which

suggests a fairly good fit and Mean Squared Error (MSE) value is 8579.35 means that the average of the squared differences between the observed values and the values predicted by the model. For Model: Ridge, the R-squared value is 0.72 means that the model also explains 72% of the variance, which refers to a similar performance to the LinearRegression model and Mean Squared Error (MSE) value is 8588.03, it is slightly higher than LinearRegression, but the difference is minimal, meaning that the model's predictions are very close. For Model: Lasso, R-squared: 0.72 means that this model performs almost similarly to the other two models with an R-squared of 0.72 and Mean Squared Error (MSE) value is 8585.22 means it is close to the Ridge and LinearRegression models. For Best Model: LinearRegression, it means that LinearRegression is selected as the best model depending on the evaluation metrics. The Cross-validated R-squared value of 0.18 with a standard deviation of 0.23 means that the model does not generalize well to new data. Lower R-squared score after cross-validation means that the model can be overfitting to the training data and it captures specific patterns in the training set that do not apply to unseen data. In conclusion, all three models are LinearRegression, Ridge and Lasso have nearly similar R-squared values and MSE, meaning similar performance on the test set. However the cross-validated R-squared value of 0.18 (with high variability) means that while the models fit the training data well, they can struggle to generalize to new data. The best-performing model, depending on this analysis is LinearRegression, but additional steps can be needed to improve its generalization performance.

2.2. Hypermeter Tuning

Based on GeeksforGeeks (2023), "In the context of machine learning, hyperparameters are configuration variables that are set before the training process of a model begins. They control the learning process itself, rather than being learned from the data." Before defining Hypermeter Tuning, the 'LinearRegression.py' script begins by importing important libraries, loading the dataset from 'dataset/Invoice.csv', and defining the feature and target variables for the regression task. In this case, frequency serves as the independent variable (feature), and amount is the dependent variable (target) to be predicted. The dataset is then split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets using the `train_test_split()` function, ensuring consistency with `random_state=42` for reproducibility. The script sets up three models: standard linear regression, Ridge regression (which uses L2 regularization to penalize large coefficients), and Lasso

regression (which applies L1 regularization to shrink some coefficients to zero, often resulting in feature selection). These models help explore different approaches to regularizing and improving the linear regression model.

```
6 # Load the dataset
7 filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
8 data = pd.read_csv(filePath)
9 # Specify the feature (X) and target (y) variables
10 X = data[['frequency']] # Replace with the actual feature column name
11 y = data['amount'] # Replace with the actual target column name
12 # Split the data into training and testing sets
13 XTrain, XTest, yTrain, yTest = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
14 # Define the models to evaluate
15 models = {
16     'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),
17     'Ridge': Ridge(),
18     'Lasso': Lasso()
19 }
```

Figure 15. Loading dataset, Specifying the feature and target, split the data and defining the models to evaluate

In the Hyperparameter Tuning, GridSearchCV is used to tune the alpha parameter for Ridge and Lasso regression models. To define Hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso, paramGrid specifies the hyperparameters (alpha parameter) that will be tuned for the Ridge and Lasso models. The higher the alpha ensures stronger the regularization effect and help to prevent overfitting by penalizing larger coefficients in the model.

```
20 # Define the hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso
21 paramGrid = {
22     'Ridge': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]},
23     'Lasso': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]}
24 }
25 # Store the best models after hyperparameter tuning
26 bestModels = {}
27 for name, model in models.items():
28     if name in paramGrid:
29         # Perform hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV
30         gridSearch = GridSearchCV(model, paramGrid[name], cv=5, scoring='r2')
31         gridSearch.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
32         bestModels[name] = gridSearch.best_estimator_
33     else:
34         # Fit the model without hyperparameter tuning
35         model.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
36         bestModels[name] = model
```

Figure 16. Define the Hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso

In the Fit Models and Tune Hyperparameters, a loop iterates over the models with two conditions. In the first condition, if the model has hyperparameters to tune (Ridge or Lasso), GridSearchCV is used to search for the best alpha value by performing 5-fold cross-validation (denoted by cv=5). The performance is evaluated using the R-squared metric (scoring='r2'). And the best model is selected and stored in the bestModels dictionary. In the second condition, if the model does not need hyperparameter tuning (LinearRegression), it's directly trained using fit() function.

2.3. Evaluation of Model Performance

The evaluation of the models, each model in bestModels is evaluated by predicting target values on the test set (XTest) and calculating performance metrics such as R-squared (r2_score) and Mean Squared Error (mean_squared_error) between the predicted (yPred) and actual (yTest) values. All these performance metrics for each model are displayed to the output screen. Another important evaluation, cross-validation is performed on the Best Model, identified by the highest R-squared score on the test set and using the cross_val_score() function, a 5-fold cross-validation is applied to the entire dataset, calculating R-squared for each fold. The mean and standard deviation of these scores are then calculated and displayed to provide an estimate of the model's generalization ability.

```
37 # Evaluate the performance of the best models
38 for name, model in bestModels.items():
39     yPred = model.predict(XTest)
40     r2 = r2_score(yTest, yPred)
41     mse = mean_squared_error(yTest, yPred)
42     print(f"Model: {name}")
43     print(f"R-squared: {r2:.2f}")
44     print(f"Mean Squared Error: {mse:.2f}")
45     print("-" * 30)
46 # Cross-validation for the best model
47 bestModelName = max(bestModels, key=lambda name: r2_score(yTest, bestModels[name].predict(XTest)))
48 bestModel = bestModels[bestModelName]
49 crossValScores = cross_val_score(bestModel, X, y, cv=5, scoring='r2')
50 print(f"Best Model: {bestModelName}")
51 print(f"Cross-validated R-squared: {np.mean(crossValScores):.2f} ± {np.std(crossValScores):.2f}")
52
```

Figure 17. Evaluate the performance of the best models

3. Model Interpretation and Evaluation

3.1. Interpretation of Model Parameters and Results

```
ModellInterpretationPTCWorkshop.py > ...
1 import pandas as pd
2 from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV, cross_val_score
3 from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression, Ridge, Lasso
4 from sklearn.metrics import r2_score, mean_squared_error
5 import numpy as np
6 # Load the dataset
7 filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
8 data = pd.read_csv(filePath)
9 # Specify the feature (X) and target (y) variables
10 X = data[['frequency']] # Replace with the actual feature column name
11 y = data['amount'] # Replace with the actual target column name
12 # Split the data into training and testing sets
13 XTrain, XTest, yTrain, yTest = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
14 # Define the models to evaluate
15 models = {
16     'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),
17     'Ridge': Ridge(),
18     'Lasso': Lasso()
19 }
20 # Define the hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso
21 paramGrid = {
22     'Ridge': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]},
23     'Lasso': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]}
24 }
25 # Store the best models after hyperparameter tuning
26 bestModels = {}
27 for name, model in models.items():
28     if name in paramGrid:
29         # Perform hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV
30         gridSearch = GridSearchCV(model, paramGrid[name], cv=5, scoring='r2')
31         gridSearch.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
32         bestModels[name] = gridSearch.best_estimator_
33     else:
34         # Fit the model without hyperparameter tuning
35         model.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
36         bestModels[name] = model
37 # Cross-validation for the best model
38 bestModelName = max(bestModels, key=lambda name: r2_score(yTest, bestModels[name].predict(XTest)))
39 bestModel = bestModels[bestModelName]
40 # Intercept and coefficients
41 intercept = bestModel.intercept_
42 coefficients = bestModel.coef_
43 print(f"Intercept: {intercept}")
44 print(f"Coefficients: {coefficients}")
45 # Interpretation:
46 # For each unit increase in the independent variable (e.g., frequency),
47 # the dependent variable (e.g., income) changes by the corresponding coefficient value.
```

Figure 18. Interpretation of model parameters and results

Soman (2024) wrote on medium.com that “Model interpretation refers to the process of understanding and explaining the behavior and decision-making process of a machine learning model.” It shifts the regression line up or down. Coefficients (slopes) represent the change in the target variable for a one-unit change in the corresponding input feature, holding all other features constant. The parameters of the Linear Regression Model, refer to the strength and direction of the relationship between each input feature and the target variable. The intercept or bias represent the predicted target value when all input features are zero essentially shifting the regression line up or down. The coefficients show how much the target variable changes with a one unit increase in the corresponding feature, assuming all other features remain constant. A positive coefficient means the feature and target have a direct relationship, while a negative coefficient signals an inverse relationship.

Output


```
Intercept: 2.9934697601469225
Coefficients: [51.99663867]
```

Figure 19. The output result of intercept and coefficients

Both intercept and coefficients are essential for understanding the linear relationship between your features and target in a linear regression model. In the output of the Intercept = 2.9934697601469225. It means that when the independent variable frequency is 0 and the predicted amount is approximately 2.99. The intercept acts as the "starting point" of the linear equation. In a linear model, it shifts the lineup or down along the vertical axis (Y-axis). In the output of the Coefficients of frequency=51.99663867. Positive coefficients (like this one) indicate that as the input feature increases, the target variable increases. If the coefficient were negative, it would mean that as the input feature increases, the target variable decreases. So, it means that for every one unit increase in the frequency feature, the predicted amount increases by approximately 51.99 units. The Interpretation of Linear Equation below represents the relationship between the feature frequency and the target amount: $\text{amount} = 2.993 + 51.997 * \text{frequency}$

frequency, if the frequency is 10, for example, the predicted amount can be: $\text{amount} = 2.993 + (51.997 \times 10) = 2.993 + 519.97 = 522.963$.

3.2. Analysis of Model Performance

For all models such as LinearRegression, Ridge, and Lasso have the R-squared value result is 0.72 means that 72% of the variance in the dependent variable (company income) has been explained by service frequency variable (independent variables). This is a good fit, meaning the models can capture the relationship between the variables fairly well. However, it also implies that 28% of the variance is unexplained, that can be due to missing features or inherent noise in the data. The Mean Squared Error values are very similar for all models: 8579.35 for LinearRegression, 8588.03 for Ridge, and 8585.22 for Lasso. This indicates that the predictions of all three models are close to the actual values on average. The small differences between MSE values suggest that the models are performing nearly identically, at least on the test data. While MSE values are similar, Ridge and Lasso may perform better on unseen data due to the regularization techniques they employ, which help prevent overfitting. The cross-validated R-squared result is 0.18 with a standard deviation of 0.23, means it is much lower than the original model's R-squared values result. This drop means that the models are overfitting to the training data and it performs well on the test set but problem to generalize to new unseen data.

3.3. Identify Model Limitations

This residual plot below compares the predicted values of amount (y-axis) against frequency (x-axis) from a Linear Regression Model. The red dashed line represents zero residuals, where prediction's reliability matches actual values. The blue dots show how far the predictions are, with residuals scattered above and below the line. At lower frequencies, the residuals are more densely clustered, suggesting that the model performs better at these values. However, as the frequency increases, the residuals spread out, indicating greater error and variability in the predictions at higher frequencies. This pattern means that the model struggles to capture the relationship between frequency and amount as frequency increases, indicating possible model limitations or issues.

```

ModelLimitationPTCWorkshop.py > ...
1  import pandas as pd
2  from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV, cross_val_score
3  from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression, Ridge, Lasso
4  from sklearn.metrics import r2_score, mean_squared_error
5  import numpy as np
6  import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
7  import seaborn as sns
8  # Load the dataset
9  filePath = 'datasets/Invoices.csv'
10 data = pd.read_csv(filePath)
11 # Specify the feature (X) and target (y) variables
12 X = data[['frequency']] # Replace with the actual feature column name
13 y = data['amount']      # Replace with the actual target column name
14 # Split the data into training and testing sets
15 XTrain, XTest, yTrain, yTest = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
16 # Define the models to evaluate
17 models = {
18     'LinearRegression': LinearRegression(),
19     'Ridge': Ridge(),
20     'Lasso': Lasso()
21 }
22 # Define the hyperparameters for Ridge and Lasso
23 paramGrid = {
24     'Ridge': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]},
25     'Lasso': {'alpha': [0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 100.0]}
26 }
27 # Store the best models after hyperparameter tuning
28 bestModels = {}
29 for name, model in models.items():
30     if name in paramGrid:
31         # Perform hyperparameter tuning using GridSearchCV
32         gridSearch = GridSearchCV(model, paramGrid[name], cv=5, scoring='r2')
33         gridSearch.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
34         bestModels[name] = gridSearch.best_estimator_
35     else:
36         # Fit the model without hyperparameter tuning
37         model.fit(XTrain, yTrain)
38         bestModels[name] = model
39 # Evaluate the performance of the best models
40 for name, model in bestModels.items():
41     yPred = model.predict(XTest)
42     r2 = r2_score(yTest, yPred)
43 # Residual plot
44 residuals = yTest - yPred
45 sns.scatterplot(x=yPred, y=residuals)
46 plt.axhline(y=0, color='red', linestyle='--')
47 plt.title('Residual Plot')
48 plt.xlabel('Predicted Values')
49 plt.ylabel('Residuals')
50 plt.show()

```

Figure 20. Model Limitations

Output:

Figure 21. The output of Residual Plot

4. AI Ethics and Fairness

4.1. Identification of Potential Biases

Based on LinkedIn.com (*How Can You Identify Bias in Machine Learning Algorithms?*, 2024), “Bias in machine learning algorithms can have serious consequences for individuals and society, such as discrimination, unfairness, and misinformation. Bias can arise from various sources, such as data, models, or human decisions. Therefore, it is important to be able to identify and mitigate bias in machine learning algorithms.” The Linear Regression Model has several potential biases, including issues from an incomplete feature set, categorical encoding, overfitting, and data imbalance. With only two features, ‘frequency’ and ‘plate_number’, the model may miss key factors like transaction time, vehicle type, or regional variations that could impact the amount, leading to a narrow perspective. Moreover, encoding ‘plate_number’ as a numerical value

assumes a relationship with the target, which may not exist, introducing unnecessary bias. Since 'plate_number' is a unique identifier with no actual connection to the 'amount', the model might overfit to random patterns, learning details that do not generalize well. Finally, if there is not a data balance such as some vehicles appearing more frequently or having higher amounts this can make the model perform very low in less common cases.

4.2. Strategy to Mitigate Potential Biases

The Linear Regression Model faces several biases, such as those arising from an incomplete feature set, categorical encoding, overfitting, and data imbalance. With only two features, frequency and 'plate_number', the model could overlook important factors like transaction time, vehicle type, or regional differences, leading to a limited view of what affects the amount. Encoding 'plate_number' as a numerical value assumes a relationship with the target that may not exist, adding unnecessary bias. Since 'plate_number' is just a unique identifier unrelated to amount, the model might pick up on random patterns that don't generalize well. Additionally, if certain vehicles appear more often or have higher amounts, the model could struggle with less frequent or smaller cases, reducing its overall performance.

Conclusion

Machine learning is one of the most important parts in information technology or data science field. Its theory and formula can be applied in cutting-edge technological fields such as in research, AI, or data analysis especially it is used other fields include business, education, government or sport. Even though new technology grows rapidly, machine learn is playing as an important role and still used along to it.

Problem formation and data preparation, model selection and training, model interpretation and evaluation, AI ethics and fairness are core concept that come from statistics plays as an important role to help many Data Scientist success working with Machine Learning.

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ITDS540 - Assignment Rubric

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EIU ID: EIU95527

Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Problem Formulation and Data Preparation	15 marks	13	
2. Model Selection and Training	25 marks	20	
3. Model Interpretation and Evaluation	25 marks	19	
4. AI Ethics and Fairness	10 marks	7	
5. Report and Presentation	25 marks	20	
<p style="text-align: center;">*** Penalty ***</p> <p style="text-align: center;">This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)</p>	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	79	